

Synthesis, spectral characterization and DNA binding properties of dinuclear copper(II) complexes with pyridinehydrazones

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Abstract : Dinuclear copper(II) complexes of functionalized heterocyclic hydrazones, viz. 2-acetylpyridine acetylhydrazone (APAH), 2-acetylpyridine benzoylhydrazone (APBH), 2-benzoylpyridine acetylhydrazone (BPAH), 2-benzoylpyridine benzoylhydrazone (BPBH) have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductivity measurements, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, infrared and electron spin resonance spectral data. Electrolytic nature of complexes is investigated by conductivity studies. IR spectral data suggest that the ligands act as neutral trifunctional NNO-donor system. Electronic spectral data suggest octahedral geometry for the complexes. Electrochemical behavior of metal complexes is investigated by using cyclic voltammetry. The complexes undergo quasi-reversible one electron reduction. Absorption titration studies revealed that these complexes are avid binder to calf-thymus DNA. The electronic absorption titrations suggest that the complexes bind DNA through intercalation involving a strong π -stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore and base pairs of DNA.

Keywords : Copper complexes, pyridine hydrazones, synthesis, spectral studies, DNA binding properties.

Introduction

The chemistry of copper complexes is of interest owing to their importance in biological and industrial processes¹. Metal complexes of hydrazones have wide applications in biological processes²⁻⁵ and as catalysts in chemical and petrochemical industries⁶⁻⁸.

The bioactivity of heterocyclic hydrazones as well as their metal complexes is of interest, especially due to their pharmacological properties⁹⁻¹¹. Metal complexes of aroylhydrazones exhibit antitumour¹² and antibacterial activity¹³. There is also much interest in the development of artificial nucleases. Artificial metallonucleases require ligands which effectively deliver metal ions to the vicinity of DNA. Investigations on metal-DNA interactions¹⁴ has been an area of active research^{15,16}. Studies on chemical modification of nucleic acids with transition metal complexes are of great interest in the design of chemotherapeutic drugs, regulation of gene expression and design of tools for molecular biology¹⁷. Copper(II) has been shown to bind the DNA bases at the N(7) of purines and N(1) of pyrimidines¹⁸.

In the light of the above and in continuation of our

ongoing research work^{19,20} a series of functionalized hydrazones (Fig. 1) have been synthesized and characterized. The design of such ligands is achieved by using corresponding precursors. A series of hydrazones have

R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = CH₃ APAH

R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = C₆H₅ APBH

R₁ = C₆H₅; R₂ = CH₃ BPAH

R₁ = C₆H₅; R₂ = C₆H₅ BPBH

Fig. 1. A general structure for ligands.

been synthesized by using aromatic carbonyl compounds and substituted hydrazides. Investigations on dinuclear copper complexes is of interest due their higher activity than the corresponding mononuclear complexes

Results and discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes are

Table 1. Analytical and molar conductivity data of copper(II) complexes

Complex	Colour (Yield, %)	Mol. wt.	Found (Calcd.) (%)				M.p. (°C)	Molar conductivity ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			C	H	N	M		
[(Cu-APAH-Cl) ₂ Cl ₂ (1)]	Dark green (72)	624 (623.28)	35.21 (34.68)	3.57 (3.55)	13.84 (13.48)	21.23 (20.38)	260–262 ^a	72.5
[(Cu-APBH-Cl) ₂ Cl ₂ (2)]	Light green (62)	748 (747.64)	45.24 (44.97)	3.61 (3.50)	11.30 (11.24)	17.21 (17.0)	270–271 ^a	90.8
[(Cu-BPAH-Cl) ₂ Cl ₂ (3)]	Green (75)	748 (747.42)	45.12 (44.99)	3.86 (3.50)	12.01 (11.24)	17.89 (17.0)	250–251 ^a	50.0
[(Cu-BPBH-Cl) ₂ Cl ₂ (4)]	Dark green (67)	872 (871.57)	53.41 (52.36)	3.96 (3.46)	9.89 (9.64)	15.32 (14.58)	295–296 ^a	49.5

^aDecomposes.

consistent with the proposed molecular formulae of complexes. The molar conductivity data (Table 1) suggest that the complexes are 1 : 2 electrolytes. The observed magnetic moment values (0.62–0.74 BM) for complexes are subnormal possibly due to the presence of antiferromagnetically coupled metal centers. In the spectra of metal complexes, a strong band in the range 24932–29762 cm^{-1} may be associated with M-L charge transfer transition. The high energy band of moderately intense band in the range 37037–37735 are assigned to intra-ligand transition band in the spectra of all metal complexes. The copper complexes showed one weak peak in 13315–14492 cm^{-1} in favour of octahedral geometry²¹.

IR spectra of ligands are compared with those of metal complexes to determine donor atoms of ligand. The IR spectra of the ligands have several prominent peaks due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ stretching modes, respectively. In the spectra of complexes, $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands are present suggesting that the hydrazone acts as neutral ligand. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ in the spectrum of free hydrazone is shifted to lower frequency in the spectra of complexes suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in chelation. IR data suggest that the hydrazone ligands act as neutral tridentate ligand in dinuclear complexes. The non-ligand bands in 566–504 and 508–468 cm^{-1} regions are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{(\text{M-O})}$ and $\nu_{(\text{M-N})}$ respectively. Heterocyclic aroylhydrazones are known⁸ to react with divalent transition metal ions and form dinuclear complexes of the general formulae $[(\text{MHL})_2]\text{X}_2$ (where, HL = heterocyclic aroylhydrazone and X = halide). Based on physicochemical and spectral data a general structure (Fig. 2) for complexes is proposed.

Fig. 2. A proposed general structure for $[(\text{CuLHCl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complexes (where LH = APAH, APBH, BPAH, BPBH).*ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes :*

ESR spectral data of complexes in solid state and in DMF are given in Table 2. ESR spectra of complexes in DMF at liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT) exhibit well resolved peaks at low field and at high field corresponding to g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} respectively. The g values were computed from the spectrum using tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) free radical as the g marker. The typical ESR spectrum of $[(\text{Cu-APAH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex is given in Fig. 3. Kivelson and Neiman²² have reported that the g_{\parallel} is less than 2.3 for covalent character and greater than 2.3 for ionic character of the metal-ligand bonding. As seen from Table 4 the g_{\parallel} values for copper complexes less than 2.3 suggesting a significant covalent character in the metal-ligand bonding. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ suggest that the unpaired electron predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital²³ characteristic of octahedral geometry for copper(II) complexes. The g_{av} value for these complexes is greater than 2 indicating the presence of covalent character²². The axial symmetry parameter (G) values of copper complexes suggest the interactions between copper centers. The or-

Table 2. The Hamiltonian and orbital reduction parameters of copper(II) complexes

Complex serial no.	In solid state				In solution				λ	K_{\parallel}	K_{\perp}	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^5$	$A_{\perp} \times 10^5$
	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	G	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	G					
1.	2.103	2.077	2.085	1.36	2.240	2.111	2.154	2.189	534	0.878	1.187	790.7	465.1
2.	2.188	2.162	2.170	1.16	2.192	2.173	2.179	1.107	671	0.726	1.381	2418.72	2418.72
3.	2.229	2.191	2.204	1.99	2.247	2.231	2.237	1.068	821	0.719	1.391	1426.11	1488.44
4.	2.185	2.170	2.175	1.089	2.2	2.182	2.188	1.097	628	0.724	1.384	2511.75	2790.84

Fig. 3. X-band powder ESR spectra of $[(\text{Cu-APAH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ at (1) 300 K and (2) at LNT. ESR spectra of $[(\text{Cu-APAH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ in DMF (3) at 300 K and (4) at LNT.

bital reduction parameters (K_{\parallel} and K_{\perp}) are calculated. The observed relation $K_{\perp} > K_{\parallel}$ for the complexes indicates the presence of significant in plane π -bonding.

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

Redox behavior of the copper(II) complexes have been investigated by cyclic voltammetry in DMF using 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAHEP) as supporting electrolyte. The cyclic voltammetric profile of $[(\text{Cu}(\text{APBH})\text{Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ is given in Fig. 4. The electrochemical data of metal complexes are presented in Table 3.

Repeated scans at various scan rates suggest the presence of stable redox species in solution. $E_{1/2}$ values of Cu^{II} complexes are respectively found in 0.269–0.325 V vs $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}^{24-27}$. It may be inferred that the Cu^{II} complexes undergo reduction to their respective Cu^{I} complexes. The non-equivalent current in cathodic and anodic peaks for complexes indicate quasi-reversible behavior²⁶. The difference $\Delta E_p = E_{pc} - E_{pa}$ in all the complexes exceeds the Nerstian requirement $59/n$ mV (n = number of electrons involved in oxidation reduction) which

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram profile of $[(\text{Cu-APBH})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}_2$ at varying scan rates (a) 25, (b) 50, (c) 75, (d) 100 mV s^{-1} .

transition. Absorption spectra of $[(\text{Cu}(\text{APBH})\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$ in the absence and in presence of CT-DNA are shown Fig. 5. The metal-free hydrazone ligands did not show any DNA binding activity. The intrinsic binding constants (K_b), was determined by using the equation,

$$[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + 1/K_b(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) \quad (1)$$

where $[\text{DNA}]$ is the concentration of DNA in base pairs, ϵ_a , ϵ_b and ϵ_f are apparent extinction coefficient ($A_{\text{obs}}/[\text{M}]$), the extinction coefficient for the metal (M) complex in the fully bound form and the extinction coefficient for free metal (M) respectively. A plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ versus $[\text{DNA}]$ gave a slope of $1/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f)$ and verti-

Table 3. Cyclic voltammogram data of copper complexes

Complex	Redox couple	E_{pc}	E_{pa}	ΔE_p (mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	$-i_c/i_a$	$\log K_c^b$	ΔG^0
$[(\text{Cu-APAH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	II/I	0.097	0.549	452	0.323	1.17	0.074	424.8
$[(\text{Cu-APBH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	II/I	0.013	0.525	512	0.269	1.78	0.065	373
$[(\text{Cu-BPAH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	II/I	0.081	0.569	488	0.325	1.62	0.068	390.4
$[(\text{Cu-BPBH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	II/I	0.042	0.545	124	0.293	4.72	0.27	1550

suggests quasi-reversible character of the electron transfer reaction²⁸. The complexes have large separation (124–512 mV) between anodic and cathodic peaks indicating quasi-reversible character. The large peak to peak separation may be due to the formation of $\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{Cu}^{1+}$ complex intermediate species in analogy with previous observation²⁹.

Electronic absorption titrations :

Electronic absorption spectroscopy is an effective method for examining the interaction of DNA with metal complexes. Hypochromic and bathochromic effects are the spectral changes when a complex interacts with DNA and forms a new complex. In general, a complex binding with DNA through intercalation usually results in hyperchromism and bathochromism of the absorption band due to the intercalative mode involving a strong π -stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore and base pairs of DNA^{30–33}. The binding interaction of complexes with CT-DNA was monitored by comparing their absorption spectra with and without CT-DNA. All the complexes exhibit an intense absorption band in 265–270 nm ($37735\text{--}37037 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) region attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$

cal intercept equal to $1/K_b(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f)$; K_b was calculated from these values. The data (Table 4) suggest that the complexes bind DNA strongly. On addition of DNA, the complexes show the absorbance of the complexes decreases (hypochromism) and absorption maximum is shifted to higher wavelength (bathochromism). These observations suggest that the complexes bind DNA through intercalation involving a strong π -stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore (pyridine moiety) and base pairs of DNA. The complexes are arranged in the increasing order of binding constants.

The order of binding constants (1) parallels with increasing hydrophobicity of ligand moieties in the complexes. Less binding constant of BPBH complex may be due to its bulky nature. The high binding constants of present complexes, for example, $[(\text{Cu-APBH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[(\text{Cu-APAH-Cl})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ may be attributed to the presence of aromatic groups in the ligand part of the complex that facilitate π -stacking interactions³⁴. Electrostatic attraction between the cationic complex and the negatively charged phosphodiester backbone of DNA may also contribute to the binding constant^{35,36}.

Fig. 5. (A) Absorption spectra of [(Cu-APBH)Cl₂]Cl₂ in the absence (top) and in the presence of increasing amounts of CT-DNA. [Arrow shows the decreasing in absorbance upon increasing concentrations DNA from top to bottom]. (B) A plot between [DNA]/(ε_a-ε_f) versus [DNA].

Table 4. Electronic absorption data upon addition of CT-DNA to the complexes

Complex	λ _{max} (nm)		Δλ	H (%)	K _b (M ⁻¹)
	Free	Bond			
[(Cu-APAH-Cl) ₂]Cl ₂	236	236.5	0.5	+34.18	6.89 × 10 ⁵
[(Cu-APBH-Cl) ₂]Cl ₂	358	359	1	+47.26	1.68 × 10 ⁶
[(Cu-BPAH-Cl) ₂]Cl ₂	239	239.5	0.5	+10.06	3.3 × 10 ⁵
[(Cu-BPBH-Cl) ₂]Cl ₂	376	378	2	+15.57	4.3 × 10 ⁴

Conclusions

The dinuclear copper(II) complexes of pyridinehydrazones are characterized based on analytical and spectral data. The data (K_b) obtained in electronic absorption titrations suggest that the complexes bind DNA strongly. The data suggest that the complexes bind DNA through intercalation involving a strong stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore (pyridine moiety) and base pairs of DNA³⁴. Electrostatic attraction between the cationic complex and the negatively charged phosphodiester backbone of DNA may also contribute to the binding constant^{35,36}.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Analytical grade 2-acetylpyridine, 2-benzoyl pyridine,

acetichydrazide and benzhydrazide were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., India. Copper chloride was purchased from Merck chemicals. The solvents used in the synthesis of ligand and metal complexes were distilled before use. Calf-Thymus DNA (CT-DNA) was purchased from Genie 79 Bio labs, Bangalore, India. All other chemicals were of reagent grade quality and used without further purification.

Preparation of ligands :

Hot aqueous solution of hydrazide (0.5 mmol) was added to a boiling solution of methanolic solution of carbonyl compound (0.5 mmol). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1 h. A pale yellow coloured crystalline products were formed in cooling the reaction mixture. The hydrazones were collected by filtration, washed several times with hot water and dried *in vacuo*. The ligands were recrystallized from methanol.

2-Acetylpyridine acetoxyhydrazone (APAH) : Yield 85%, m.p. 162–164 °C, elemental analysis : C, 61.32 (61.00); H, 6.50 (6.25); N, 24.0 (23.71); IR spectra : 3185, 1678, 1620 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν(NH), ν(C=O) and ν(C=N) stretching vibrations respectively. The ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ solvent : δ (2.4) (singlet 3H), (2.5) (singlet 3H), (7.25) (singlet 1H), (7.75–7.85) (multiplet 4H), are respectively assigned to -CH₃ (carbonyl),

-CH₃ (hydrazine), NH- and pyridine protons. LC-MS spectrum of HL shows molecular ion peaks at (*m/z*) 177.

2-Acetylpyridine benzoyl hydrazone (APBH) : Yield 80%, m.p. 145–147 °C, elemental analysis : C, 68.75 (70.27); H, 5.50 (5.47); N, 17.12 (17.56); IR spectra : 3177, 1654, 1616 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν(NH), ν(C=O) and ν(C=N) stretching vibrations respectively. The ¹H NMR spectra of HL was recorded in CDCl₃ solvent. Signals of HL at δ (2.5) (singlet 3H), (7.25) (singlet 1H), (7.75–7.85) (multiplet 9H), (6.7) are respectively assigned to -CH₃, >NH- and aromatic (pyridine + phenyl ring) protons. LC-MS spectrum of HL shows molecular ion peaks at (*m/z*) 239.

2-Benzoyl pyridine acetylhydrazone (BPAH) : Yield 83%, m.p. 81–90 °C, elemental analysis : C, 71.20 (70.27); H, 5.70 (5.45); N, 17.96 (17.56); IR spectra : 1666, 1586 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν(C=O) and ν(C=N) stretching vibrations respectively. The ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ solvent : δ (1.80) (singlet 3H), (7.40) (singlet 1H), (7.42–8.80) (multiplet 9H), (6.7) are respectively assigned to -CH₃, >NH- and aromatic (pyridine + phenyl ring) protons. LC-MS spectrum of HL shows molecular ion peaks at (*m/z*) 239.

2-Benzoyl pyridine benzoylhydrazone (BPBH) : Yield 72%, m.p. 135–137 °C, elemental analysis : C, 75.9 (75.72); H, 5.23 (5.01); N, 14.02 (13.94); IR spectra : 1685, 1598 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν(C=O) and ν(C=N) stretching vibrations respectively. The ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ solvent : δ (7.22) (singlet 1H), (7.30–8.80) (multiplet 13H), are respectively assigned to imine (>NH-) and aromatic (one pyridine + two phenyl ring) protons. LC-MS spectrum of HL shows molecular ion peaks at (*m/z*) 301.

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes were prepared by mixing hot aqueous solution of CuCl₂·6H₂O and ligand in a molar ratio of 1 : 1. To the boiling solution of ligand (0.01 mol) in methanol (100 ml) was added CuCl₂·6H₂O (0.01 mol) dissolved in minimum quantity of water and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2 h. Crystalline complexes which separated out were collected by filtration, washed with hot water, small quantity of methanol and hexane and dried *in vacuo*. Analytical data of complexes are given in Table 1.

The elemental analyses were performed at RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow. Molecular weights of the complexes were determined by using Rast's method. Magnetic measurements of complexes were carried out at 298 K in Faraday's magnetic susceptibility balance (Sherwood Scientific, Cambridge, UK). High purity pentahydrated copper sulphate was used as a standard. The conductivity measurements at 298 ± 2 in dry and purified DMF were carried out on CM model 162 conductivity cell (ELICO). The electronic spectra of metal complexes were recorded in DMF with UV lamda 50 (Perkin-Elmer) spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ with Perkin-Elmer spectrum 100 spectrometer in KBr discs. ESR spectra were recorded in Varian E-112 X-band spectrophotometer at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT) in both solution (DMF) and solid state. The cyclic voltammetry was performed with a CH Instruments 660C electrochemical analyzer and a conventional three electrode configuration with glassy carbon working electrode, silver/silver chloride reference electrode and platinum counter electrode. Nitrogen was used as a purge gas and all solutions were 0.1 M concentration in tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆) supporting electrolyte.

DNA binding experiments :

Interaction of complexes with calf thymus DNA was studied by electronic absorption spectroscopy. All the experiments involving interaction of the complexes with CT-DNA were carried out in a water buffer containing 5 mM Tris(hydroxyl methyl) ammonia methane (Tris) and 50 mM NaCl and adjusted to pH 7.0 with HCl. The solution of CT-DNA in 5 mM Tris-HCl/50 mM NaCl gave a ratio of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm (*A*₂₆₀/*A*₂₇₀) of 1.8–1.9, indicating that the DNA is sufficiently free from proteins³⁷. A concentrated stock solution of DNA was prepared in 5 mM Tris-HCl/50 mM NaCl in water at pH 7.0 and the concentration of CT-DNA was determined per nucleotide by taking the absorption coefficient (6600 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) at 260 nm³⁸. Stock solutions are stored at 4 °C and were used after no more than 4 days. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare buffer solutions. An appropriate amount of metal complex was dissolved in a solvent mixture of 1 vol.% DMF and 99 vol. % Tris-HCl (5 mM tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl, pH 7.0) buffer at the concentration of 1.0 × 10⁻⁵ M. Absorption

titration experiments were performed by maintaining the metal complex concentration constant while gradually increasing the concentration of CT-DNA within 0–100 μM .

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